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2 vanadium catholyte
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6 Highlights

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- 11 1 Alkaline lignin was combined with a small amount of multiwalled carbon nanotubes.
- 12 2 Lignin-based monoliths were added to the catholyte reservoir.
- 13 3 The catholyte's thermal stability was extended to a temperature of 45°C.
- 14 4 The discharge capacity surpassed the maximum theoretical capacity of the catholyte by
15 18%.

16 A mediated vanadium flow battery: Lignin as redox-targeting active material in the 17 vanadium catholyte

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24 Abstract

25 Vanadium Redox Flow Batteries (VRFB) are promising candidates for stationary energy storage
26 but show certain drawbacks at low energy densities ($<30 \text{ Wh L}^{-1}$) and a narrow operating
27 temperature range (15-40°C). The latter is mainly caused by the limited stability of the catholyte
28 at elevated temperatures. Therefore, in this work we introduce a stability enhanced vanadium
29 catholyte with redox mediating properties conferred by the highly abundant organic polymer lignin
30 to achieve higher performance in temperature range for a penetration of the VRFB systems in
31 thermal applications. By reducing the vanadium concentration to 0.9 M the catholyte's stability is
32 significantly improved so that a wider operational temperature window for the flow cell can be
33 exploited. To compensate the loss in energy density lignin as a solid capacity booster is added to
34 the positive reservoir. Herein, the feasibility of lignin in combination with multiwalled carbon
35 nanotubes as solid charge storage material is investigated by cyclic voltammetry and
36 charge/discharge cycles at temperatures from 10°C to 45°C. Volumetric capacities $>28 \text{ Ah L}^{-1}$ are
37 achieved for the capacity-boosted VRFB with 0.9 M catholyte that are comparable with the
38 conventional 1.8 M vanadium electrolyte. The use of an abundant renewable resource like lignin
39 in the VRFB could not only increase cell performance but also attribute to lower the high
40 operational costs and environmental impact of the battery.

41 *Keywords:* energy storage, lignin, redox targeting, vanadium

42 1. Introduction

43 Redox flow batteries (RFBs) play a fundamental role in energy storage technologies. Compared
44 to conventional static batteries they persuade with the possibility of fast mechanical charging and
45 the independent scaling of energy and power due to a decoupled system [1-3]. Thus, RFBs are an
46 interesting alternative for energy storage at large scale stationary applications to facilitate the
47 integration of renewable energy sources in the electrical grid. Various RFB chemistries are
48 currently commercialized. Among these, the vanadium redox flow battery is the most developed
49 and is widely used for large-scale energy storage up to the range of MW/MWh [4]. However, a
50 broad market penetration is still affected by limitation factors like a low energy density, high cost

51 of vanadium and narrow operational temperature range [5, 6]. Commercial vanadium electrolyte
52 usually consists of a vanadium concentration of 1.5 – 2.0 M by which energy densities of 19-38
53 Wh L⁻¹ are reached [3]. One of the most critical issues that limit energy density and lead to a
54 restricted temperature window, results from the low solubility and stability of the positive
55 electrolyte solutions [5]. To attain higher energy densities, higher vanadium concentrations are
56 necessary which approaches the saturation and solubility limits of the vanadium species and
57 reduces the operating temperature window. The main problem is the catholyte which contains VO₂⁺
58 ions. At temperatures above 40°C the VO₂⁺ ions react irreversible to the less soluble vanadium
59 pentoxide which then precipitates [3]. Thus, VRFB systems usually employ electrolyte cooling
60 and heating systems to maintain the temperature between 15°C and 40°C. Therefore, there has
61 been a wide research effort to increase the stability of the electrolyte by the use of organic and
62 inorganic additives. However, the practical application of additives showed capacity losses due to
63 their oxidation by the VO₂⁺ ions [3, 7, 8, 9]. Besides technological restrictions, the VRFBs also
64 suffer from a negative economic and ecological impact. Among the redox flow batteries, the
65 vanadium battery has the highest environmental impact due to corrosiveness, non-sustainability,
66 and low availability of vanadium. Additionally, the low energy density induces the need of a large
67 amount of electrolyte volume, which leads to high overall operating costs due to the high material
68 price of vanadium.

69 An approach to overcome these drawbacks, is to lower the vanadium concentration in the
70 electrolyte and simultaneously introduce a redox-targeting compound to compensate the lowered
71 capacity. Although redox mediation is not a novel concept, this strategy has only been applied in
72 a limited number of flow battery prototypes. In redox mediating batteries the energy is stored in
73 active materials that do not flow with the electrolyte but are confined in the reservoir. The transfer
74 of charge is achieved by soluble redox mediators in the electrolytes. Wang et al. proposed redox-
75 targeting-based lithium flow batteries using LiFePO₄ and LiTi₂(PO₄)₃ as solid energy storage
76 materials in the catholyte and anolyte reservoirs and achieved capacities that are 4-6 times larger
77 than of the vanadium redox flow battery [10, 11]. In this battery system ferrocene and
78 dibromoferrocene serve as soluble mediators in the catholyte and cobaltocene and bis
79 (pentamethylcyclopentadienyl)cobalt in the anolyte that are oxidized/reduced on the electrodes in

80 the cell during the charge cycle. Whereas, LiFePO_4 and $\text{LiTi}_2(\text{PO}_4)_3$ are stored in the respective
81 reservoirs and are oxidized/reduced by the mediators [10, 11, 12]. Chen et al. developed a low-cost
82 and high-capacity redox-targeting electrolyte system using ferrocyanide/ferricyanide as soluble
83 species and Prussian blue a solid active material stored in the reservoir. They introduced this
84 electrolyte system in a $\text{Zn}/[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$ -PB flow cell and in a $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-/3-}/\text{Br}^-$ flow cell with
85 Prussian Blue as solid active material in the anolyte and catholyte reservoirs receiving a high
86 volumetric capacity of 61.6 Ah L^{-1} [13]. Furthermore, Paez et al. reported mediated alkaline flow
87 batteries with commercial $\text{Ni}(\text{OH})_2$ electrodes confined as solid material in the reservoir where
88 they increased the storage capacity in the catholyte to 29 Ah L^{-1} where without the presence of
89 $\text{Ni}(\text{OH})_2$ it is limited to 7.2 Ah L^{-1} [14]. In another study, Zanzola et al. introduced conductive
90 composite of polyaniline and carbon black as a solid charge storage material with Fe(III/II) and
91 V(IV/III) as soluble mediator in an aqueous electrolyte system. Applied in a flow cell they
92 achieved a capacity of 64.8 mA h g^{-1} at a current density of 38.5 mA cm^{-2} which is three times
93 higher in comparison to the bare electrolyte without polyaniline [15].

94 In general, redox targeting reactions in RFBs include two sorts of reactions, an electrochemical
95 reaction on the electrode and a redox-targeting reaction in the reservoir. Solid energy storage
96 materials are stored in the catholyte and/or anolyte tank, while mediators act as transporters of
97 electrons between the electrodes and materials. Since the energy density of conventional RFBs is
98 limited by the low solubility of the active species in electrolyte, the addition of solid charge storage
99 materials has proven to be a successful method to increase the volumetric energy density and
100 enhance the overall performance of RFBs [16, 17].

101 For the VRFB, only one redox-mediating method has been published so far, which is based on
102 Prussian blue as the solid active material. Cheng et al. presented this all vanadium redox-targeting
103 battery where granules of Prussian blue analogue (PBA) are introduced in the catholyte reservoir.
104 As PBA/PB has the same redox-potential as $\text{VO}^{2+}/\text{VO}_2^+$ it reduces/oxidizes the vanadium species
105 in the catholyte reservoir leading to an enlargement in the catholyte charge and discharge capacity
106 of the flow cell. They hereby reduced the vanadium concentration of the catholyte to 0.6 M and
107 achieved a high catholyte capacity density of 44.6 Ah L^{-1} which is almost three times the
108 theoretical capacity [18]. However, the combination of Prussian blue in diluted sulphuric acid, that

109 is present in commercial vanadium electrolytes, is a risk factor for the battery safety as it can lead
 110 to the production of hydrogen cyanide (HCN), which is extremely poisonous and flammable.
 111 Additionally, PBA is not naturally occurring and must first be synthesised which complicates its
 112 use in industrial applications.

114 Figure 1 Schematic illustration of the concept of a redox-targeting VRFB with solid lignin
 115 monoliths in the catholyte reservoir during the charging process. Positive and
 116 negative half-cell are separated by a Nafion membrane. The catholyte with the
 117 dissolved VO^{2+}/VO_2^+ species acts as a mediator and stores charge energy in the
 118 solid active material confined in the reservoir.

119 Therefore, alternative materials for the vanadium chemistry still need to be found. Herein, we
 120 present experimental results for an all VRFB using alkaline lignin combined with a small amount
 121 of multi walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) as capacity booster in the positive compartment.
 122 The use of lignin in the battery industry has several advantages. Since lignin is a naturally
 123 occurring biopolymer and is discarded in the paper industry as by-product, it is a highly abundant
 124 and low-cost material that is redox active due to its phenol groups [19, 20]. In previous studies
 125 lignin-based electrolytes were developed for the use in flow batteries that proved the reversibility
 126 of the redox reaction and the feasibility of its use as electrochemical active material [20, 21]. To
 127 the best of our knowledge, this is the first literature report on the use of organic electrode materials
 128 as redox mediators/booster in acidic electrolytes. In previous work, we demonstrated that lignin
 129 could act as a charge carrier in the catholyte and, when coated onto a carbon felt electrode, leads
 130 to significant capacity enlargements in the positive half-cell [22]. However, the coating also caused
 131 a higher internal cell resistance that limited the capacity increase. In this work, we take advantage

132 of charge carrier ability of lignin and simultaneously avoid a rise in the overpotential when
133 charging and discharging the battery. Therefore, the lignin-based precursor solution was coated on
134 a 3D printed cubic structure consisting of multiple hollow octahedra (hereinafter called monoliths)
135 that were immersed in the catholyte reservoir. We demonstrate that by reducing the concentration
136 of the electrolyte to 0.9 M, it is possible to provide a permanent stability of the catholyte at an
137 elevated temperature of 45°C maintaining a capacity above 28 Ah L⁻¹. Since lignin is an
138 inexpensive material, highly abundant and environmentally friendly [23, 24, 25, 26], the cost and
139 environmental impact of the vanadium redox flow battery can be significantly improved.
140 Additionally, by lowering the viscosity of the electrolyte pumping costs can be reduced. Figure 1
141 illustrates the working principle. The electrolytes containing V²⁺/V³⁺ and VO²⁺/VO₂⁺, respectively
142 are pumped into a flow cell, where the vanadium species are electrochemically reduced and
143 oxidized at the electrodes. To provide an examination of the capacity, the volume of the catholyte
144 is half of the volume of the anolyte so that the capacity is limited by the catholyte. By adding the
145 solid lignin material to the catholyte reservoir, the VO²⁺/VO₂⁺, species are chemically reduced or
146 oxidized by lignin in the reservoir, while the battery is charged and discharged. Thus, an extension
147 of the charge and discharge in capacity is achieved and additional capacity is gained.

148 2. Materials and methods

149 2.1. Preparation of the electrolyte

150 A vanadium electrolyte solution of 0.9 M concentration contained in 4.55 M sulphuric acid and 25
151 mM phosphoric acid is used in the galvanostatic charge and discharge experiments. The electrolyte
152 was prepared from a 1.8 M vanadium commercial solution (Oxkem Limited, United Kingdom) in
153 which the vanadium species V³⁺/VO²⁺, are present in a 50:50 mixture together with 50 mM of
154 phosphoric acid and 4.6 M total sulphuric acid. This electrolyte is diluted to a solution of 0.9 M
155 vanadium concentration by adding 4.5 M sulphuric acid. For cyclic voltammetry experiments, a
156 catholyte solution of 0.45 M total vanadium in a 50:50% mixture of VO²⁺/VO₂⁺, is used. The 0.45
157 M solution was obtained from the 0.9 M by charging it to a SOC of 50% and afterwards diluted
158 with deionized water to a solution of 0.45 M vanadium concentration.

159 2.2. Preparation of lignin as solid active material

160 The lignin precursor solution was prepared from 5 g lignin, alkali (Sigma Aldrich) and 0.5 g
161 graphitized multiwalled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs, nanografi, >99.99%) which were mixed
162 and then ball milled for 30 minutes at 400 rpm at 10 minutes intervals. Subsequently, 8-10 ml of
163 1-Methyl-2- pyrrolidone (99.0%, Sigma Aldrich) was added and the mixture was stirred for 20
164 minutes with an ultrasonic overhead stirrer. The viscous ink was further modified to form pellets
165 or to be coated onto a solid structure. For the preparation of pellets, the ink was filled into a syringe
166 to form small droplets onto a glass substrate which were immediately vacuum dried at 65°C for
167 24 h to form solid pellets (Figure 2). For the coating on a solid structure, monoliths consisting of
168 multiple hollow octahedral made of photo curable resin forming a cubic structure were 3D printed
169 to a dimension of 1.5 cm × 1.5 cm × 1.5 cm. The monoliths were immersed into the ink for 2
170 minutes to ensure an overall coating and immediately vacuum dried at 65°C for 24 h or until the
171 coating was completely dried (Figure 2).

172 2.3. *Physical characterization*

173 To analyse the morphology of the coating, scanning electron microscopy was performed with a
174 Jeol JSM-6500F field emission electron microscope at an operating voltage of 15 kV and a
175 working distance of 10 cm. Different magnifications of ×500, ×3000, and ×35000 were applied.

176

177 2.4. *Electrochemical characterization*

178 Electrochemical characterization of the lignin coating was carried out by cyclic voltammetry in a
179 three-electrode cell. A lignin coated glassy carbon, a platinum mesh and a Ag/AgCl (in 3.5 M KCl)
180 served as working, counter- and reference electrodes. The electrodes were tested in different
181 solutions, firstly a 2.0 M H₂SO₄ and secondly in a 50% charged vanadium catholyte with a
182 vanadium concentration of 0.45 M was used. The tests were carried out under inert gas atmosphere
183 with a permanent nitrogen flow. The scans were recorded with a Biologic VMP3 multichannel
184 potentiostat–galvanostat (Biologic, France) at a scan rate of 10 mV s⁻¹.

185

186

187 Figure 2 Lignin-based pellets (left) and 3D printed cube coated with lignin-based ink (right).

188 Galvanostatic cycling was carried out in a single filter-pressed flow cell with graphite felt
189 electrodes (Sigracell felt GFD 2.5EA) of 9 cm² projected area. The electrodes were pre-treated
190 thermally in air at 500°C for 1 h in a Carbolite Laboratory Chamber Furnace. A proton exchange
191 membrane (Nafion NR 212, Ion Power) separated the half-cells. The electrolyte of 0.9 M vanadium
192 concentration was pumped from the sealed reservoirs into the cell using a Masterflex pump (L/S
193 Variable-Speed Digital Drive with Remote I/O, 6 to 600 rpm; 90 to 260 VAC) at a fixed of 50 mL
194 min⁻¹. During the cycling, the reservoirs were kept under a permanent argon flow. The charge
195 and discharge cycles were recorded with a Neware BTS4000 series battery tester (Neware
196 Electronic Corporation, Shenzhen, China). The charge cycles were limited by a cut-off cell voltage
197 of 1.9 V, while the discharge cycles were cut off at 0.7 V. Between each charge and discharge
198 cycle a 10-minutes open circuit voltage period was recorded. The start volume of the catholyte and
199 anolyte was 80 ml each for the first cycles to analyse the overall performance of the cell and obtain
200 a steady capacity. When discharged, the cell was set to a long resting period in order to reduce the
201 volume in the catholyte reservoir to 40 ml. The cell was charged and discharged for various cycles
202 in this configuration, maintaining 80 ml in the anolyte and 40 ml in the catholyte reservoir. The
203 capacity is now limited by the catholyte volume and is taken as a reference capacity. After the
204 discharge, the cell is kept in a resting period again, and the coated monoliths were added to the
205 positive reservoir. Several cycles were then recorded in this configuration while the monoliths
206 were confined in the positive reservoir. Current densities of 7.5, 15, 30, 45, 60 and 75 mA cm⁻²
207 were applied. Furthermore, the thermal operational range of the system was studied in a climate
208 chamber (Ineltec CM-4800 model) performing the above written procedure of charge and
209 discharge cycles but varying the environmental temperature to 10°C, 30°C and 45°C.

210 3. Results and discussion

211 3.1. Physical characterization

212 Figure 3 SEM images of the 3D printed cubes coated with the lignin-based ink at
213 magnifications of $\times 500$, $\times 3000$ and $\times 35000$.

214 The morphology of the coating is visualized in scanning electron microscopy images (Figure 3).
215 It can be observed that the coating adheres to the porous structure of the 3D printed cube (Figure
216 3a) representing the surface structure of the 3D cube that provides a large contact area between
217 coating and electrolyte. The distribution between lignin and the MWCNTs is represented in Figure
218 3b, showing a rough surface layer consisting of the MWCNTs and lignin. Since the MWCNTs
219 provide an increased conductivity, higher magnifications of $\times 35000$ could be applied showing the
220 individual nanotubes in the coating (Figure 3c).

221 3.2. Electrochemical characterisation

222 Electrochemical analysis of the interaction between vanadium and lignin was first carried out by
223 cyclic voltammetry. For this, the ink containing lignin and multi-walled carbon nanotubes (as
224 prepared in section 2.2) was coated on a glassy carbon electrode. Since the commercial vanadium
225 electrolyte consists of $4.6\ \text{M}\ \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$, the lignin coated electrode was firstly analysed in a $2\ \text{M}$
226 sulphuric acid solution to get an understanding of the electrochemical activity of lignin in its
227 reduced form. Figure 4 shows a comparison of cyclic voltammograms on a bare glassy carbon and
228 a lignin coated glassy carbon electrode in $2\ \text{M}\ \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$, and in $0.45\ \text{M}$ vanadium catholyte.

229 The CV in H_2SO_4 demonstrates that for plain lignin two oxidation peaks (at $0.41\ \text{V vs. Ag/AgCl}$ V
230 and at $0.67\ \text{V vs. Ag/AgCl}$) and two reduction peaks (at $0.34\ \text{V}$ and at $0.54\ \text{V vs. Ag/AgCl}$) are
231 obtained. This leads to redox-potentials of $E = 0.38\ \text{V vs. Ag/AgCl}$ and $E = 0.61\ \text{V vs. Ag/AgCl}$
232 in agreement with literature values [27, 28, 29]. These peaks show that lignin has multiple
233 functional groups for electron transfer reactions. Furthermore, the reactions of an untreated glassy

234 carbon electrode and a lignin coated glassy carbon electrode in the vanadium catholyte were
235 compared. The oxidation and reduction peaks of the $\text{VO}^{2+}/\text{VO}_2^+$ species are seen at 1.23 V and
236 0.31 V *vs.* Ag/AgCl respectively, whereas the oxidation and reduction peaks for $\text{VO}^{2+}/\text{VO}_2^+$
237 species combined with lignin occurred at 1.05 V *vs.* Ag/AgCl and 0.82 V *vs.* Ag/AgCl, respectively.
238 As it can be observed in Figure 4, the peak-to peak separation decreases when lignin is added to
239 the glassy carbon, from ΔE_p 0.92 V to ΔE_p 0.23 V. This indicates the reversibility and kinetics for
240 $\text{VO}^{2+}/\text{VO}_2^+$ redox transformations have been improved upon lignin modification. On the other
241 hand, current densities have increased by 4.5 mA cm⁻² for oxidation and by 0.33 mA cm⁻² for
242 reduction for lignin combined with vanadium, and the ratio of the cathodic to the anodic peak
243 current has increased from 0.63 for only vanadium to 0.96 for vanadium combined with lignin.

244 Since the coating on the GC consists of 91% wt. lignin and 9% wt. MWCNTs it has to be
245 mentioned that these improvements can be attributed to both components of the coating. Previous
246 studies already reported that MWCNTs have an electrocatalytic activity on the $\text{VO}^{2+}/\text{VO}_2^+$ reaction
247 [30, 31]. However, their effect is comparatively low and their proportion in this coating is small.
248 Thus, their use in the coating is rather to achieve a better conductivity and it can be assumed that
249 they have just a minor impact on the increase in reversibility of the $\text{VO}^{2+}/\text{VO}_2^+$ reaction. The
250 significant increase in current density and the results obtained from charge and discharge cycles
251 that are discussed later in this section show that these effects can be largely attributed to a redox
252 reaction between lignin and vanadium. These facts confirm that the redox reaction of $\text{VO}^{2+}/\text{VO}_2^+$
253 tends to become more reversible after a beneficial mediation by lignin and let suggest that
254 combining lignin together with $\text{VO}^{2+}/\text{VO}_2^+$ may lead to transformations in the structure of the lignin
255 molecule promoting a shift of the redox potential and changes in its electrochemical behaviour.

256
 257 Figure 4 Cyclic voltammograms on a bare glassy carbon and a lignin coated glassy carbon
 258 electrode in 2 M H₂SO₄, and on a bare glassy carbon electrode and a lignin coated
 259 glassy carbon electrode in 0.45 M vanadium catholyte, scan rate 10 mV s⁻¹.
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261
 262 To enable the reaction between lignin and the VO²⁺/VO₂⁺ ions in a flow battery, and to ensure the
 263 confinement of lignin in the reservoir while the flow cell is in operation, solid lignin containing
 264 pellets or monoliths were manufactured (Figure 2). Then, charge and discharge cycles were
 265 performed in a single flow cell configuration.

266

267

268 Figure 5 Voltage profile of the VRFB before and after reducing the volume and adding lignin
 269 monoliths to the positive reservoir. The blue line indicates a configuration with 80
 270 ml of volume in both electrolyte reservoirs. The yellow line demonstrates a
 271 configuration with 80 ml of anolyte volume and 40 ml of catholyte volume, so that
 272 capacity is limited by the positive half-cell. The red line shows the mediating
 273 configuration with 80 ml of anolyte volume and 40 ml + 5 monoliths (1.13 g lignin)
 274 in the catholyte reservoir.

275

276 Tests were carried out adding either pellets or monoliths to the positive reservoir. For experiments
 277 with pellets, a special configuration of reservoirs with filters was installed to prevent the pellets
 278 from leaving the reservoir. For experiments with monoliths, conventional beakers were used as
 279 reservoirs. The size and structure of the monoliths ensure a confinement of the solid material in
 280 the reservoir and prevent it from being carried with the electrolyte flow. In this way, lignin does
 281 not reach the inlet of the cell and is not part of the reactions taking place at the electrodes during
 282 charge and dis- charge. Galvanostatic charge and discharge cycles were performed following the
 283 procedure in 2.4 to compare the capacity enhancing effect for different variables, like total lignin
 284 mass, current density and temperature. During the charge process, VO^{2+} ions flow from the
 285 reservoir into the cell and are oxidized to VO_2^+ at the positive electrode. The VO_2^+ ions are then,
 286 when reaching the reservoir again, being chemically reduced to VO^{2+} by lignin in an interfacial
 287 charge-transfer process, while lignin itself is oxidized and stores the charge packed in the

288 monoliths immersed in the reservoir. During discharge, the reverse reactions take place, first the
289 VO_2^+ ions flow from the reservoir into the cell and are reduced to VO^{2+} species which flow to the
290 reservoir and when in contact with the oxidized lignin are chemically oxidized to the
291 VO_2^+ meanwhile lignin is reduced. The voltage-capacity profiles of the cell before and after
292 reducing the catholyte volume by half and adding lignin monoliths to the reservoir are represented
293 in Figure 5. First, cycles were performed with an initial electrolyte volume of 80 ml in the catholyte
294 and anolyte reservoirs, obtaining charge and discharge capacities of 1.76 Ah and 1.44 Ah,
295 respectively (Figure 5 blue line). For an evaluation the theoretical volumetric capacity was
296 calculated with Faraday's law (1) in order to compare the capacities with the maximum possible
297 capacity that can be obtained for this system when the cell is 100% charged.

$$298 \quad Q = \frac{m}{M} Fz \quad (1)$$

299 F is Faraday's constant (96485 C mol^{-1}), z the number of electrons interchanged, and m and M are
300 mass and molar mass of vanadium, respectively. The calculation for a 0.9 M concentrated
301 electrolyte with a volume of 80 ml in each reservoir gives a theoretical capacity of 1.93 Ah. Thus,
302 the cell could be charged and discharged with capacities of 91% and 75% of the theoretical values
303 when charged and discharged, respectively, obtaining a Coulombic efficiency of 82%.

304 Afterwards, the cell configuration was changed to a volume of 80 ml in the anolyte reservoir and
305 40 ml in the catholyte reservoir. The reason to use half volume in the catholyte reservoir was to
306 evaluate if lignin would be able to compensate for the lower electroactive species available in the
307 positive compartment. This configuration forces a limitation in capacity by the positive half-cell
308 and enables room for a visible capacity increase. Figure 5 (yellow line) shows that after reducing
309 the volume to 40 ml in the positive reservoir, in the absence of lignin, a charge capacity of 0.83
310 Ah and discharge capacity of 0.58 Ah was obtained. Considering a maximum theoretical value of
311 0.96 Ah, a state of charge of 86% after charge and 26% after discharge was reached. When adding
312 five lignin monoliths with a total mass of 1.13 g to the catholyte reservoir, a significant increase
313 in charge and discharge capacity by 424 mA h and 380 mA h, respectively, was obtained (Figure
314 5 red line). Thus, a total capacity of 1.25 Ah after the charge and slightly above 0.96 Ah after the
315 discharge was achieved that surpassed the theoretical capacity for 100% SoC for the 40 ml
316 electrolyte volume and proved the mediating functionality of lignin to vanadium.

317 Aiming to analyse the temperature effect on the mediating properties of lignin, charge and
 318 discharge cycles were tested at different environmental temperatures, using a 1.5 m × 1.7 m × 1.9
 319 m walk in climate chamber in order to maintain a given constant temperature during the charge
 320 and dis- charge cycles. Figure 6 shows the discharge capacity of the cell containing a volume of
 321 80 ml in the anolyte reservoir and a volume of 40 ml + 5 monoliths supporting lignin in the
 322 catholyte reservoir at different temperatures and varying current densities.

323
 324 Figure 6 Evaluation of capacity for charge (solid line) and discharge (dashed line) cycles
 325 with varying current densities at different temperatures after adding 1.13 g lignin.
 326

327 With the presence of lignin in the catholyte, values >1 Ah were obtained for all current densities
 328 tested for T = 30°C and 45 °C. For 10°C the threshold of 1 Ah was achieved at current densities
 329 <40 mA cm⁻². These capacity values surpassed the theoretical value of 0.96 Ah (for 40 ml
 330 electrolyte volume) and validates the redox targeting process in a broad operational temperature
 331 range. However, at 10°C the capacity decreases remarkably to 0.34 Ah for current densities above
 332 40 mA cm⁻² so that highest capacities were achieved at current densities between 15 and 30 mA
 333 cm⁻². Notable is the stable operation at 45°C with capacity values above 1.2 Ah for the charge and
 334 1.14 Ah for the discharge for several current densities, leading to volumetric capacities of 30 Ah
 335 L⁻¹ after the charge and 28.5 Ah after the discharge. Thus, a 20% and 18% capacity improvement

336 in charge and discharge, respectively, when compared with the theoretical volumetric capacity of
337 a 0.9 M concentrated electrolyte (24.1 Ah L^{-1}).

338 A stability test of the system's performance at a constant environmental temperature of 45°C was
339 done as the cell was continuously in operation for more than 7 days performing charge and
340 discharge cycles at different current densities.

341

342

343 Figure 7 Cyclability tests at an operational temperature of 45°C for a total duration of
344 more than 7 days with 40 ml catholyte volume and lignin in the catholyte reservoir.
345 The figures show voltage profile, capacities and efficiencies (Coulombic efficiency
346 red line, energy efficiency yellow line, voltaic efficiency blue line) for varying
347 current densities.

348

349 In Figure 7, the capacity values for different current densities are plotted over cycles. 13 cycles
350 correspond to a total operational time of 7 days. The current density was changed from 7.5 to 75
351 mA cm^{-2} to investigate the cell's stability in capacity and efficiency at 45°C . Even after several
352 cycles, capacities above 1.1 Ah could be observed, leading to volumetric capacities of 27.5 Ah L^{-1}
353 which competes with the commercial 1.8 M concentrated vanadium electrolyte. For the different
354 current densities Coulombic efficiencies between 75% and 96% and energy efficiencies between

355 60% and 73% were achieved. Altogether, a steady performance in charge and discharge capacities
356 could be observed over the entire period demonstrating that the mediating cell works at high
357 temperatures without any restrictions. Since the vanadium concentration is reduced to 0.9 M, this
358 electrolyte is stable at a high temperature range. While the conventional 1.8 M electrolyte is limited
359 to an operational temperature $<40^{\circ}\text{C}$ [32, 32].

360 It should be noted that for the total theoretical capacity of the solid monoliths not only lignin but
361 also the graphitized multi-walled carbon nanotubes need to be considered. Previous studies
362 confirmed that multi-walled carbon nanotubes act as a catalyst with good performance to the
363 cathode reactions [34, 35, 30]. In these studies, a small capacity gain from 52 mAh with pristine
364 carbon felt electrodes to 60 mAh with modified CF/carboxyl MWCNTs electrodes was stated [26].
365 However, in our experiments the total coating mass consists of 91% lignin and 9% graphitized
366 multi-walled carbon nanotubes. Since the amount of carbon nanotubes is quite low, their
367 contribution to the capacity increasing effect is considered to be small. Due to the complexity of
368 lignin's molecule, that also varies with its source of origin and method of extraction, lignin's
369 theoretical capacity is difficult to estimate. To evaluate the relation between capacity enhancement
370 and total amount of added material, the number of added monoliths was varied in different
371 experiments. Figure 8 represents an evaluation of obtained capacity gain in relation to the total
372 added lignin mass either in pellets form or coated on monoliths. In these plots only the mass of
373 lignin (not the entire coating) is taken into account. Figure 8a shows the voltage-capacity profiles
374 for various experiments by varying the mass of added lignin either as pellets (LP) or as monoliths
375 (LM) to the catholyte reservoir. For the use of lignin monoliths a general better cell performance
376 with an associated higher capacity increase was observed. This can be attributed to the cell design.
377 For the addition of pellets to the reservoir special filters between reservoir and cell were in-
378 stalled to prevent a possible flow of the pellets into the cell. For the addition of monoliths no extra filters
379 were needed which facilitated the operation and also reduced the possibility of leakages in the
380 system. It can be observed that in the charge-discharge experiment for 0.76 g LM a higher
381 overpotential is obtained compared to the other tests performed which leads to an increased voltage
382 in the charge and a decreased voltage in the discharge. Since all experiments were performed under
383 the same conditions, this occurrence may be related to the performance of the flow cell system as,
384 depending on the number of monoliths added to the reservoir and their location inside the reservoir,
385 these could be an obstacle for an optimized electrolyte flow and could lead to a reduced availability

386 of active vanadium species at the electrodes during the time of charging and discharging.
387 Therefore, for the methodology of this redox-targeted system still requires some improvements in
388 the set-up by re- designing the reservoirs or find alternative ways of increasing the contact of lignin
389 with the electrolyte but at the same time avoiding that it would be a blockade in the electrolyte
390 flow. Nevertheless, this curve gives an indication for the received performance of adding different
391 quantities of lignin to the electrolyte. In Figure 8b the gain of capacity by either adding lignin
392 pellets (LP) or lignin monoliths (LM) is demonstrated. For both types, the increase flattens with
393 higher amount of material, which could be caused by a possible disruption in the electrolyte flow
394 through the solid material. In case of the monoliths: taken into consideration that 1g of coating
395 needs a structure of approximately 3-4 monoliths, the ratio between solid material in the reservoir
396 and electrolyte volume leads to a barrier in the electrolyte flow. Thus, this configuration with 40
397 ml of electrolyte volume leads to a limitation in capacity gain in the range of some 400 mAh.

398 From the experimental data a volumetric capacity of the coating is estimated to be 10 Ah L⁻¹.
399 Following the calculations from [18] and [14] the theoretical capacity of a solid battery material
400 Q , can be determined by the Faraday's constant, the molecular weight of lignin (M), the number
401 of exchange electrons (n) and the density of lignin (ρ), using the following formula:

$$402 \quad Q = \frac{26.8 \text{ Ah mol}^{-1}}{Mn\rho} \quad (2)$$

403 However, for lignin the calculation of its theoretical capacity has proven to be more complex.
404 Since the molecule is heterogeneous, the degree of polymerisation is difficult to measure.
405 Therefore, the number of its monomer units is not well determined. This impedes the determination
406 of the exchange electrons that take place in the reaction with vanadium. Due to the presence of
407 numerous p-hydroxyphenyl, guaiacyl and syringyl groups, it can be assumed that several electrons
408 are exchanged in the reaction with the VO²⁺/VO₂⁺ ions.

409

410

411

(a)

412

413

(b)

414 Figure 8 Capacity gain for adding pellets or monoliths with varying mass of lignin. a)
 415 Voltage-capacity profiles after adding different amount of lignin monoliths (LM) or
 416 lignin pellets (LP). b) Capacity gain ΔC from 40 ml volume without lignin and 40
 417 ml + lignin in the positive reservoir for varying amount of added lignin.

418 4. Conclusions

419 The evidence of reactions between lignin and $\text{VO}^{2+}/\text{VO}_2^+$ could be proved and the energy density
420 for the 0.9 M concentrated vanadium catholyte has significantly increased by adding lignin. Lignin
421 serves as a solid redox-targeting material to store the energy in the catholyte reservoir and capacity
422 gain is observed in both directions: during the charge and discharge cycles of the battery. It is
423 assumed that the redox reactions between lignin and $\text{VO}^{2+}/\text{VO}_2^+$ are reversible. The mediating
424 system was stable for more than 7 days at an elevated temperature of 45°C, obtaining high
425 volumetric capacities of 28.5 Ah L⁻¹ that surpassed the maximum volumetric capacity for a 0.9 M
426 vanadium electrolyte by 18% (24.1 Ah L⁻¹), leading to energy and Coulombic efficiencies of 72%
427 and 95%, respectively. Therefore, better thermal stability and an overall improvement of the
428 battery's performance in economic and ecologic terms could be achieved by elaborating the
429 mediating design. The kinetics of charge transfer reaction rate need to be studied in more detail as
430 well as the maximum possible capacity gain, taken into consideration that there is room for more
431 possibilities. The experiments with pellets and monoliths demonstrated that the form in which
432 lignin was added influenced cell performance and capacity gain. Thus, the utilization of lignin as
433 solid capacity booster and its distribution in the reservoir can still be advanced. An improvement
434 in the kinetics of the chemical reaction between lignin and vanadium could be achieved by re-
435 designing the reservoir and/or re-shaping the solid material in order to provide a higher active area
436 of solid material and thus, enlarge the solid liquid contact in the reservoir. It is expected that this
437 work offer a new concept for the commercial application of VRFBs.

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